

HANGING GARDENS: TRANSFORMING SPACES WITH SUSPENDED BEAUTY

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Abstract

Hanging baskets have evolved beyond traditional gardening tools to become innovative solutions for urban green spaces. Hanging baskets now serve as integral components of urban green infrastructure, contributing to environmental sustainability by improving air quality, reducing urban heat and increasing biodiversity. They offer a unique combination of aesthetic appeal and ecological benefits in residential gardening. This abstract explores the multifaceted nature of hanging baskets, emphasizing their design principles, practical benefits and diverse applications. The benefits of hanging baskets are manifold; they provide spatial efficiency, enhance urban and residential green spaces and support plant growth in constrained environments. Additionally, hanging baskets offer solutions for vertical gardening, allowing for the cultivation of flowers, herbs and vegetables in limited spaces.

Key words: Hanging baskets, urban green spaces, residential gardening, vertical gardening.

Introduction

Today's floriculture market offers a plethora of new vegetative annuals. Their growth patterns may be trailing or strong, making them ideal for hanging basket or container garden culture. Gardeners today led hectic lives and housing might be cramped, leaving little space for gardening. All of these aspects add to the popularity of hanging baskets (24). Flowering or foliage plants drooping in baskets suspended from any support are referred to as hanging baskets. Hanging baskets work best with delicate, light-weight trailing or cascading plants. Hanging baskets are suitable for both indoors and outside. They can be shown on verandas, the doorway to the house, balconies and in roof gardening (13). Hanging baskets look great in conservatories, too. Hanging baskets are an excellent material for enhancing the appearance of a wedding hall, party plot, or restaurant. These can be hung from trees, lamp poles, fences, or on stands outside (8).

Hanging baskets can be used to successfully grow a variety of tropical and annual bedding plants. Hanging basket production allows greenhouse producers to make money by utilising space above work benches, floor space and pathways (1). Hanging baskets can attract a higher price (per plant) than tiny containers or flats, boosting the profitability of greenhouse bedding plants. Growers may devote whole or portions of greenhouses to hanging basket production (7).

Reasons to adopt

Hanging baskets helps in decorating the apartment blocks and high buildings.

It also provides aesthetic values to the space.

It helps in conserving the water (9).

It helps in improving the air quality

Too small yard space for much variety (1).

Need for mobility to "follow the sun" or for variety.

Easy root pruning.

Easy to relocate (26).

Characteristics of the container

Clean, attractive and easy to handle.

Light in weight but durable.

Easy to hang.

Side openings for plantation in the pot are preferable.

Make sure the containers have an adequate number of exit holes in the bottom for excess water to drain away

Should have hooks to hang on a stand (25).

Types of containers**Clay terracotta**

Terracotta containers are inexpensive and easily accessible. Unglazed clay ceramics are porous and will absorb moisture from the potting soil. Soil in these pots will dry up faster, which might be beneficial for plants that favour a drier growth environment (3). These containers also have a tendency to fracture if left outside during winter. Because these containers are permeable, salts that build inside them will ultimately seep through the clay wall to the outside (10).

Glazed ceramic

Glazed ceramic containers are not porous like unglazed containers, thus they will not draw moisture from potting soil. But they're just as robust (3). Some of the smaller glazed pots come with matching ceramic trays affixed to the bottom to collect runoff. These pots are ideal for smaller herbs (12).

Plastic

These are the garden containers of choice. They are lightweight and retain moisture in the soil. However, when exposed to the sun, it becomes extremely hot, which can quickly scorch a plant's roots (3). When exposed to sunlight, some plastic containers, particularly those not meant for gardening, degrade and break apart over time. Unlike ceramic, plastic is incredibly easy to drill and cut through (15).

Wood

Wood planters look excellent and, if properly maintained, may last for several seasons. Cedar is the greatest wood for outdoor usage in terms of both affordability and durability. Redwood, cypress and teak also hold up against the weather, although they cost far more than cedar (3). Although wooden containers appear great, they may be hefty and take up a lot of room. To prolong their life, line them with strong plastic or use an inside plastic container to retain potting soil (19).

Fiberglass container

In commercial planting, fiberglass containers are frequently utilized. The surface may be easily shaped into a variety of bespoke forms to suit any style and is long-lasting. These containers are not porous in nature. Often, bottom surfaces have ridges incorporated into them to offer drainage isolation. They cost a great deal more than plastic containers (22).

Metal container

Aluminium, copper, brass and stainless steel are often utilized metals in the building of containers. The metals' reflective property creates a visually appealing contrast and gives the planting area depth. Metals require more upkeep than other surface materials (23).

Media**Sand**

Sand is occasionally added in baskets to improve drainage. Sand does not absorb water, thus baskets containing sand in their potting soil will drain more easily (4).

Humus

It has excellent water retention characteristics, contains numerous trace elements and minerals that plants need and creates a good dwelling habitat for helpful bacteria (17).

Peat moss

Peat moss has incredible water retention capabilities. It is fibrous and light, with a wonderful spongy texture. Gardeners use it to lighten their soils and it is the most frequent and plentiful ingredient in potting soils (18).

Perlite

Perlite, an enlarged type of volcanic glass, is extremely lightweight and porous, making it ideal for minimising soil compaction and enhancing water retention (14).

Filling

Filling with medium and planting is an easy way to manage plastic and wood. In the case of wired containers, you must first line the container with something to prevent dirt from spilling out. Pre-formed coir basket liners were utilised for this purpose (2). The container must be filled with media after lining. An inner lining of a thin gunny fabric is placed in the hanging basket container and around 2-3 cm thick sphagnum or sheet moss is sprinkled over it. A single layer of sphagnum moss can also be sprinkled throughout the container. The containers can be filled with compost consisting of equal parts peat moss or coco-peat, leaf mould, garden loam, sand and farm yard manure. Water-absorbing crystals can also be added to the medium. To remove air pockets, gently firm the dirt around the roots. Water well until water has soaked the mix and flows out the drain openings (21).

Plant selection

It should thrive under local climatic conditions

Fast growing or proliferating

Spreading type or trailing or cascading habit with shallow fibrous root system (6).

Easy to propagate

Shallow rooted plants are ideal

Select the plants with low requirement of nutrients (9).

Planting

Fill the basket with media, then lay the plant in the middle and pack with prepared soil. After spreading soil around the plant, fully soak the basket in water before hanging it in place. Hanging baskets dry fast due to their constant exposure to air on all sides. It is important to keep the soil hydrated (27).

After care

Watering

In a hot, sunny location, watering is required every day. Terracotta pots, in particular, typically require more regular watering. If you want to use less water, put a water-retaining substance into your potting soil. Keep in mind that water requirements vary with the weather. If it's moist, no water is required (20). The hanging basket is thoroughly watered with a fine rose can. Water can be slowly poured from the top, leaving enough time between two applications for the water to absorb (15).

Fertilization

Baskets quickly deplete fertiliser due to their small root capacity and big plant growth. When fertiliser is depleted, plants stop growing and blooming slows or ceases. Baskets must be fed on a regular basis, every seven to fourteen days, using liquid feed. Alternatively, a slow-release formulation should be employed. Controlled release formulations (CRF) may be ideal for the homeowner (10).

Liquid fertilizers of NPK and micro-nutrients can be applied in small quantity as soil drench and as foliar spray @ 1 % at 15-30 days interval. 1-2 g of NPK mix (19: 19: 19) dissolved in 1 litre of water can also be used (16).

Grooming

Pinching slightly below the faded blossom can induce new blossoms (deadhead). Trim drooping leaves and dead blooms every two to three weeks. Some plants, like verbena and lantana, require little to no pruning. Begonias and impatiens are commonly cut to make "balls of colour" (20).

Repotting

When roots grow through the drainage holes at the bottom of the grow pot or planter, it is time to repot. It entails gently removing the plant from its existing planter or grow pot, loosening the roots, and cutting off one-third of the roots. The tap root may also be trimmed if fibrous and lateral roots are abundantly growing. After that, remove the old potting mix, add the new mix, and lastly replant (11).

Examples

Flowering: *Abutilon megapotamicum*, *Allamanda*, *Achimenes*, *Begonias*, *Browallia*, Cascade Chrysanthemum, Cascade Petunia, *Clianthus* (*C. dampieri* and *C. puniceus*), *Campanula* (*C. isophylla* and *C. primulinum*), Flame Violets (*Episcias*), Fuchsias, *Impatiens sultanii*, *Lantana* (dwarf, trailing) and Lipstick plant (*Trichosporum lobbianum*).

Foliage: Asparagus fern (*Asparagus plumosa* and *A. sprengeri*), Coleus, Ferns (native and exotic species), Kangaroo vine (*Plectranthus australis*), vining Philodendron, *Pothos*, Smilax, Spider plant (*Chlorophytum elatum*), *Rhipsalis* spp., *Tradescantia* species and *Zebrina pendula* (both Wandering Jew), *Vinca major* and common mint.

Cacti and succulents: Burro tail (*Sedum morganianum*), Carrion flower (*Stapelia nobilis*), Ice plant (*Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*) and Wax plant (*Hoya carnosa*).

Conclusion

Urbanization often leads to deforestation and increases the construction rate, which results in disappearing of green areas in towns and cities. In such cases, hanging baskets offers a versatile and attractive option to add greenery for balconies, patios and other spaces. They also help in improving the air quality by absorbing the pollutants and leads to healthier living environment. Furthermore, it offers an eco-friendly solution to promote green spaces in urban areas, contributing for environmental sustainability and improved quality of life.

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